

TEXTURAL CHARACTER AND ORGANIC MATTER CONTENT OF THE SEDIMENTS OF THE CHILKA LAKE, ORISSA, EAST COAST OF INDIA

Anilkumar, R, Pallavi, A, Kaladhar, R, and Kasipathi, C

Department of Geology, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India

Abstract: Chilka Lake is a brackish marine lagoon in the Orissa State, India. The Lake is divided into the Outer Channel, the Northern Sector, the Central Sector and the Southern Sector for the present study. The Lake is considered as a combination of (i) estuarine, (ii) lagoonal and (iii) lacustrine environments. A total of fifty sediment samples were collected in May and December, 2009 from the Lake for the determination of textural character and organic matter (O.M.) content. The sediment type is characterized by sand, silty sand, muddy sand, clayey sand and sandy clay at different parts of the Lake. The O.M. content of the sediments ranges from 0.31% in May to 2.1% in December. The variation in O.M. content depends on the nature of the substrate and the availability of the source material (phytoplanktons, nutrients, etc.) in the Lake. O.M. is an important source material for the generation of hydrocarbons under favourable conditions.

Key words: Chilka Lake, East Coast, Sediments, Textural character, Organic matter.

INTRODUCTION

Chilka Lake is a brackish water lagoon, spread over the Puri, Khudra and Ganjam District of Orissa State on the east coast of India, at the mouth of Daya River, flowing into the Bay of Bengal. It is the largest coastal lagoon (1165 km²) in India and the second largest in the world and is located between 19° 25' and 19° 54' N and 85° 6' and 85° 38'E. It can be said that the Chilka Lake is a combination of three major environments: (i) estuarine (ii) lagoonal and (iii) lacustrine environments (Fig.1.).

(i) ESTUARINE CHARACTERS: As the waters from various rivers are drained into the Bay of Bengal flowing through this Lake, it has the estuarine characters towards the sea where the freshwaters are influenced by the saline water of the sea, salinity being extended toward the other sides of the Lake where the freshwaters are drained into the Lake by a number of rivers and streams.

(ii) LAGOONAL CHARACTERS: The Lake is separated from the sea by a 183 to 274 m wide spit and sea water enters into the Lake through various channels, especially at the time of high tide. Hence, it has the characters of a lagoon.

(iii) LACUSTRINE CHARACTERS: The Chilka Lake is landlocked on three sides and is separated from the sea by a sand spit and receives water from the land by various inflowing rivers and streams from the catchment area. It being a large Lake

receives water, whenever there are rains. Hence, this Lake, as the name indicates, has the lacustrine characters. Because of the above said complex characters, it attracted the interest of the Researchers to investigate the character of the sediments and to evaluate the organic matter content of the sediments.

GEOLOGY

Geological studies indicate that the coast line extended along the western shores of the Lake in the Pleistocene era with its northeastern region lying under the sea. That the coast line has moved eastward over the ages is supported by the fact that the nearby Konark Sun Temple, built originally on the seashore a few hundred years ago, is now about 3 km away from the coast.

The catchment area of Chilka Lake has a rock, sand, and mud strata. It contains a wide range of sedimentary particles such as clay, silt, sand, gravel and shells but the majority of the catchment area is characterized by containing silt. The Daya and Bhargavi rivers and other streams deposit about 1.6 million metric tons of silt into the Chilka Lake (Iwasaki, Shimpei, 1998).

According to the investigations by Chilka Lake Development Authority (CDA, 2008), Orissa, it is conjectured that a rise in worldwide sea levels over the last 6000 to 8000 years occurred with a pause in the rise of sea level about 7,000 years ago, which could have resulted in the formation of sandy beach near the coast at the Southern Sector. With rise in the sea level, the sand beach grew gradually,

Fig. 1. Map Showing General Location of the Chilka Lake

progressed seaward to the northeast and formed the spit of Chilka Lake. A fossil unearthed from the southern edge of the spit indicates that the Lake was formed about 3,500 to 4,000 years ago. The abrupt change in the direction of the coast north of the Lake, strong winds shifting sand to the shore, long shore drift (littoral drift), the presence or absence of strong river or tidal currents in different areas are the reasons attributed for the growth of the spit (CDA, 2008).

White bands of coral in the Southern Sector, at a height of 8 m, above the present water level shows that the area was once of marine and that the water was much deeper than present (Murray, A. S. and Mohanti, M. 2008).

GEOGRAPHY AND TOPOGRAPHY

Chilka Lake is a shallow bar-built estuary with large areas of mudflats. The western and southern margins of the Lake are fringed by the Eastern Ghat hill range (Tripathy, Balaram. 2007-11).

Several inland rivers, which bring silt into the Lake, control the northern end of the Lake. A 60 km long barrier beach called Rejhansa (Singh *et al.* 2005) formed by northerly currents in the Bay of Bengal, resulted in the formation of this shallow Lake and forms its eastern side. As an ephemeral Lake, its water surface area varies from 1,165 km² in the summer monsoon season to 906 km² in the winter dry season.

The Lake has numerous islands. The larger islands, separated by shallow channels, lie between

the barrier and the main body of the Lake. A total 42 km² of channels connect the Lake with Bay of Bengal (Choudhury and Janmejay, 2007-11). The six major islands are Parikud, Phulbari, Berahpura, Naupara, Nalabana, and Tampara. These islands, together with the Peninsula of Malud, constitute the Krishnaprasad revenue block of Puri District (CDA, 2008).

The north shore of the Lake is part of Khudra District and the western shore is part of Ganjam District. Due to siltation, the width of the barrier has fluctuated and the mouth of the sea has periodically been closed. The location of the mouth has also frequently shifted, generally towards the northeast.

The depth of the Lake varies from 0.3 m to 0.8 m in the dry season to 1.8 m to 4.2 m in the rainy season. The width of the old channel to the sea, now reported to be about 100 m, is known as Magarmukha (Mouth of crocodile). The Lake is divided into four separate zones, viz., the Southern, Central and Northern Sectors, and the Outer Channel area. The 32 km long Outer Channel connects the Lake with the Bay of Bengal at Arakhuda village. The Lake is vaguely pear-shaped and has a maximum length of 64.3 km with a mean width of 20.1 km (ILEC- International Lake Environment Committee, 2005).

Fig. 2. Location of Stations in the Chilka Lake

HYDROLOGY

The hydrological subsystems control the hydrology of the Lake. The land based system comprises distributaries of the Mahanadi River on the northern side, 52 river channels from the western side and the Bay of Bengal on the eastern side. Two of the three southern branches of the Mahanadi River that trifurcates at Cuttack, feed the lake. 61 % (850 cubic meters per second) of the total freshwaters inflow into the Lake is contributed by these two branches.

The second drainage system which is non-perennial accounts for 39 % (536 cubic meters per second). The important rivers of this drainage system are the Kansari, the Kusumi, the Janjira, and the Tarimi rivers. The annual total surface freshwater input to the Lake is estimated to 1.76 cubic kilometers including direct precipitation over the Lake contributing 0.87 cubic kilometers. All the inland river systems discharge an annual flow of about 0.375 million cubic meters of freshwater which is estimated to carry 13 million metric tons of silt into the Lake. On the northeast a channel connects the Lake to the Bay of Bengal.

CLIMATE

The general climate that prevails in the Lake area is of a tropical monsoon variety. Both the south-west and the north-west monsoons are experienced by the Lake area in the months of June to September and November to December, with average rain fall

of 1,238.8 mm, with 72 rainy days, respectively. 39.9° C has been recorded as the highest temperature in the Lake and 14° C has been the lowest recorded temperature in the areas surrounding the Lake. The wind speed varies from 5.3 to 16 meters per hour with southerly and southeasterly direction due to the influence of the south-west monsoon and from north and northeasterly direction during the rest of the months [Chilka Lake Development Authority (CDA, 2008).]

WATER QUALITY

According to the investigations by Chilka Lake Development Authority (CDA, 2008) the Lake water is alkaline, pH ranging from 7.1 to 9.6. The Southern Sector of the Lake has highest alkalinity.

Salinity levels in the Lake show wide temporal and spatial variation due to complex blend of freshwater discharge, evaporation and tidal inflow of sea water.

The dissolved oxygen values range from 3.3 to 18.9 ml/l. Phosphate phosphorus, nitrate nitrogen and silicates are high in the north and northwest parts of the Lake where most of the rivers discharge into the Lake with large amounts of silt and nutrients (CDA, 2008).

Bathymetry survey indicates extreme shallow depths in the Northern Sector, with less than 1.5 m in a large area. The summer water depth here is around 0.5 to 1 m. It receives water from the tributaries of the river Mahanadi, mainly Daya. The

Fig.3. Sediment Nomenclature Based on Sand- Silt – Clay Ratios (after Folk 1968a.)

Central Sector has a water depth ranging from 2 to 3 m. The Outer Channel connects the Lake to the sea in this segment. The Southern Sector of the Lake has recorded the maximum depth of 3.9 m. The average water depth of the Outer Channel is 1m in summer, and about 2 m during monsoon season.

The surface water temperature is closely related to the air temperature. It shows seasonal variation and ranges from 24.5° C in post-monsoon to 30.4° C in pre-monsoon seasons. The bottom water temperature is almost same as that of the surface temperature and is highest during pre-monsoon (32° C) and reaches lowest during post-monsoon, especially in November (27.5° C).

METHODOLOGY

Sediment samples for sediment texture analysis and for the estimation of O.M. were collected from fifty stations (Fig. 2.) in May and December, 2009 (Pre-monsoon and Post-monsoon seasons) from the Lake in the following way.

Bottom sediment samples from the shallower water areas, especially in the Outer Channel, were collected using Phleger type corer. A 40 cm PVC tube of about 4 cm inner diameter was manually driven into the sediment vertically. As the tube was pulled out of the sediment the lower end of the tube was closed with the palm to prevent the sediment from slipping out. The tube was brought to the bank of the Lake and the core was slowly pushed up the core tube and the sediment sample was collected into a polythene bag. Van-Veen grab was used to collect sediment samples from deep waters

of the Lake from the location where the sediment core was taken 100 to 200 grams of material from approximate 1cm thick sediment layer was scraped and preserved in a labelled polythene bag for sediment texture and organic matter content determinations.

ESTIMATION OF SAND, SILT AND CLAY RATIOS

Numerous methods are available for both dispersion and size analysis of sediments (Krumbein and Pettijohn, 1938; Muller, 1967; Carver, 1971). Most of the sediment samples under study are composite types containing sand, silt and clay in varying proportions. They were therefore initially dispersed with sodium hexametaphosphate solution of 0.025 N and kept overnight. The disaggregated material was washed through a BSS 240 mesh sieve having openings of 0.066 mm until clear water passes through but care was taken that washings did not exceed 1000 ml. The suspension mixture was analysed for silt and clay size particles by the pipette method in accordance with the procedure outlined by Krumbein and Pettijohn (1938). The material retained on the sieve is dried and weighed which gave the weight of material coarser than 1/16 mm, i.e., sand. The respective weights of sand, silt and clay that constitute the sediment were converted into weight percentages and plotted on a trilinear diagram with its apexes representing 100 % sand, silt and clay, and any point within the diagram represents a mixture of these three components. It may be stated that no completed mechanical analysis of sediment has been attempted.

The trilinear plots have been widely used by engineers, agronomists and geologists alike, but these plots are variously divided to denote sediment textures. Geologists generally use the plots of Trefethen (1950), Krumbein and Sloss (1951), Folk (1954) and Shepard (1954). Here Folk's textural nomenclature has been used to describe the textures of sediment (Fig. 3).

ESTIMATION OF ORGANIC MATTER CONTENT

The term organic matter is used to designate that portion of sediment, which has arisen through organic activity and which contains carbon in any form other than mineral carbonate (Sverdrup *et al.*, 1942; Trask, 1939). Very often organic matter of sediments and soils is estimated by determining organic carbon by dry combustion, wet combustion

Table 1. Outer Channel

Station Numbers	Sediment type	Organic Matter (%)	
		May & Dec.	May
1	Sand	0.3	0.4
2	Sand	0.3	0.4
3	Sand	0.3	0.4
4	Sand	0.3	0.4
5	Sand	0.3	0.4
6	Silty sand	0.3	0.4
7	Muddy sand	0.4	1.0
8	Clayey sand	0.4	0.9
9	Clayey sand	0.9	1.1
10	Clayey sand	1.0	1.1
11	Clayey sand	1.2	1.9
12	Clayey sand	1.3	1.4
13	Clayey sand	1.4	2.0
14	Clayey sand	1.4	1.9
15	Sandy clay	1.3	1.3

Table 2. Northern Sector

Station Numbers	Sediment type	Organic Matter (%)	
		May & Dec.	May
16	Sandy clay	1.1	1.2
17	Clayey sand	0.9	1.0
18	Clayey sand	0.8	0.9
19	Sandy clay	1.4	1.7
20	Sandy clay	1.5	1.7
21	Sandy clay	1.3	1.6
22	Sandy clay	1.2	1.6
23	Sandy clay	1.8	2.1
24	Sandy clay	1.7	2.0
25	Sandy clay	1.6	1.9
26	Clayey sand	1.5	1.8
27	Sandy clay	1.6	1.9
28	Sandy clay	1.6	1.9
29	Sandy clay	1.1	1.7
30	Sandy clay	1.1	1.8

or titrimetric methods. Organic carbon values are multiplied by a factor of 1.72 to obtain organic matter values, especially when sediment organic matter content is land-derived.

An aliquot of 0.5 gm of dried and ground sediment sample was placed in 500 ml conical flask. Ten ml of 1N potassium dichromate solution was pipetted on to the soil, and the two were mixed. Twenty ml of concentrated sulphuric acid containing 0.1 gm of silver sulphate was added and mixed by gentle rotation for one minute. The mixture was allowed to cool for 30 minutes. A standardisation blank (without soil) was run in the same way.

The solution was diluted to 200 ml with distilled water and 10ml of 85 % phosphoric acid, 0.2 gm of sodium fluoride and 30 drops of diphenylamine indicator were added. The solution was black-titrated with 0.5 N ferrous ammonium sulphate solution. The end point was indicated by a brilliant green.

The organic matter was calculated by the equation

$$\% \text{ OM} = 10 \left(1 - \frac{T}{S} \right) \times 1.34$$

where S is the standardisation blank titration, ml ferrous solution and T is the sample titration, ml ferrous solution. The factor 1.34 is derived as follows:

$$(1.0 \text{ N}) \times \frac{12}{4000} \times \frac{1.72}{0.77} \times \frac{100}{0.5} = 1.34$$

In which 0.5 is the sample weight, 1.72 the factor for organic matter from carbon, and 12/4000, the meq. weight of carbon. The 77 % recovery factor found by Walkley was used.

RESULTS

The textural characters of the sediments and their O.M. content analyzed as per the procedures described previously are shown in the following Tables.

DISCUSSION

Sediment characters: It is estimated that 13 million tones of silt is brought annually into the Lake by rivers and rivulets that open into it (CDA,

Table 3. Central Sector

Station Numbers	Sediment type	Organic Matter (%)	
		May & Dec	May
31	Sandy clay	1.4	1.6
32	Sandy clay	1.3	1.5
33	Clayey sand	1.4	1.7
34	Clayey sand	1.4	1.8
35	Clayey sand	1.3	1.1
36	Clayey sand	1.3	1.2
37	Sandy clay	1.4	1.7
38	Sandy clay	1.4	1.7
39	Clayey sand	1.4	1.5
40	Clayey sand	1.4	1.6
41	Clayey sand	1.5	1.6
42	Clay sand	1.4	1.6
43	Clay sand	1.4	1.6
44	Clay sand	1.4	1.5
45	Clay sand	1.4	1.4

Table 4. Southern Sector

Station numbers	Sediment type	Organic Matter (%)	
		May & Dec	May
46	Clay sand	1.2	1.4
47	Clayey sand	1.2	1.3
48	Clayey sand	1.2	1.3
49	Clayey sand	1.2	1.3
50	Clayey sand	1.2	1.3

2008). In the Lake, the sediments are mostly mud (silt + clay) in the Northern, Central and Southern Sectors, but with an admixture of mud and fine sand at the western shore of the Southern and Central Sectors. The eastern shore of the Central and Southern Sectors consists of sand. The bottom of the Outer Channel is sandy. The sediments of the Lake become coarser with distance towards the mouth of the Outer Channel and also, there is a seaward decrease in mud. The sedimentation rates in the three sectors of the Lake are 7.6 mm in the Northern Sector, 8.0 mm in the Central Sector, and 2.8 mm in the Southern Sector. The Lake has different deposition zones with comparatively higher sedimentation rate in Northern and Central

Sectors and a slow rate in the Southern Sector (CDA, 2008). In the present study it is observed that sand occurs at the mouth, clayey sand in the Outer Channel, sandy clay in the Northern Sector, and clayey sand in the Central and Southern Sectors (Tables 1-4).

Organic matter content of the sediments:

Organic matter content of sediment ranges from 0.31 to 1.4 % in May and from 0.4 to 2.0 % in December in the Outer Channel. It varies from 0.9 to 1.8 % in May and from 0.9 to 2.1 % in December in the Northern Sector. It ranges from 1.3 to 1.5 % and from 1.1 to 1.8 % in May and December respectively in the Central Sector. It ranges from 1.1 to 1.2 % in May and is 1.3 % in December in the Northern Sector (Tables 1-4, and Figures 4A, 4B, 4C and 4D). The sediments of the Northern Sector consist of somewhat higher organic matter by the inflowing rivers and streams into the Lake. Sand is poor and sandy clay and clayey sand are rich in organic matter content especially in December.

The mean organic matter content in the sediments is 1.29 % (Northern Sector), 0.31 % (Central Sector), 0.19 % (Southern Sector) and 0.19 % (Outer Channel), [Patnaik (1987)]. It is thus seen that organic matter content is highest in the Northern Sector not only because of the dense growth of macrophytes there but also due to the fact that numerous rivers that open into it bring in large quantity of organic matter. There is a seaward decrease in total organic matter content. In the present study the organic matter content ranges from 0.3 to 2.1 %. It almost matches with the readings by Patnaik (1971).

In general, the source materials for the O.M. are phanerogams, microphytobenthos, macroalgae, phytoplankton, zooplanktons, proteins, carbohydrates (glucose, cellulose and starches), lipids (oil and fats), lignins (in plants), etc. All these source materials are available in the Chilka Lake. Some are indigenous and some are transported and deposited from terrestrial areas by the inflowing rivers and streams.

The requirements for high O.M. in sediments are light (for photosynthesis), temperature, nutrients, low turbidity, phytoplanktons (photosynthesizing algae), bacteria, zooplanktons, etc. which are sufficiently available in the Chilka Lake.

The O.M. is well preserved at most parts of the Lake due to the deposition of huge amounts of sediments by many rivers and streams as described earlier.

Fig. 4A

Fig. 4B

Fig. 4C

Fig. 4D

Fig. 4. Diagrams Showing Variation in Organic Matter Content in the Sediments of the Chilka Lake

Importance of organic matter: The organic matter (O.M.) is considered as an important source material for the generation of hydrocarbons under favourable conditions. The clays and shales which

consist of abundant O.M. are considered as source rocks for petroleum.

Quantitative production of the likely products when organic matter in sediment is “cracked” under natural conditions is of major importance in hydrocarbon exploration and geochemistry” (Saxby, J.D.). “Source rocks generate and expel petroleum when sufficient thermal energy is imparted to the sedimentary organic matter (kerogen) to break chemical bonds” (Clifford C Walters).

Methane is produced from the O.M. due to bacterial action; due to the increase in temperature, O.M. gives rise to kerogen and bitumen and finally to oil and gas plus residue.

Saline-lake deposits of Cretaceous age are among the most important petroleum source rocks in China (Sun *et al.*, 1997). Saline lakes possess several characteristics that are favourable to the formation of hydrocarbons. Among these are high primary productivity, favourable enrichment and preservation conditions, abundant organic matter, and a high conversion rate of organic matter to hydrocarbons (Sun *et al.*, 1997). Hence, the Chilka Lake, in course of time, may become an important area for the generation and accumulation of hydrocarbons due to the deposition of huge amounts of sediments, especially of clayey type, and due the presence of high percentages of organic matter.

CONCLUSIONS

Chilka Lake is the largest coastal lagoon (1165 km²) in India and the second largest in the world. It is a combination of three major environments: (i) estuarine, (ii) lagoonal and (iii) lacustrine environments. It is divided into four segments: (i) the Outer Channel, (ii) the Northern Sector, (iii) the Central Sector and (iv) the Southern Sector. Huge amounts of sediments are deposited in the Lake by numerous inflowing rivers and streams and some amount of sediments are also deposited by the waves and currents from the sea. Clayey type of sediments dominates the other type of sediments. Organic matter percentage is more in the Northern Sector and the Central Sector. The sediments of the Lake have the characters of a source rock for petroleum due the presence of sufficient organic matter and the Chilka Lake, in course of time, may become the important area for the generation and accumulation of hydrocarbons under favourable conditions.

Acknowledgements: Thanks are due to Prof. C. Kasipathi, the then Head of the Department of Geology, Andhra University, for providing necessary laboratory facilities to carry out the research work. We are thankful to Prof. T.Y. Naidu and Prof. D. Deva Varma, Department of Geology, Andhra University for their help at various stages of the research work. Thanks are due to the Chilka Lake Development Authority (CDA) for giving permission to collect sediment samples from the Lake. The financial assistance from UGC-SAP in the form of J. R. F. for carrying out this work is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- Anil Kumar, R. (2009). "Ecology of Recent Foraminifera from the Chilka Lake, Orissa, East Coast of India" Ph.D. thesis submitted to Andhra University, Visakhapatnam. (Unpublished)
- Carve, R. E. (Editor). (1971). *Sedimentary petrology*. John Wiley and sons, Inc., London, 653p.
- Chilka Lake Development Authority, Orissa. (2008). "History of Chilka Lake"
- ChilkaLake Development Authority 2008. "About Chilka" [http:// www.chilka.com/about.htm](http://www.chilka.com/about.htm)
- Chilka Lake. (2008). "Welcome to Chilka Lake Lagoon" [http:// www.chilka.com/home.htm](http://www.chilka.com/home.htm)
- Choudhury and Janmejay, (2007-11). "Nature Queen Chilka and Eco- Tourism", Orissa Review (Govt. of Orissa): pp. 17-19
- Clifford C Walters. "Origin of Petroleum". Exxon Mobil Research & Engineering Co. Annandale, N J 08801 Chapter 2.
- Folk, R. L. (1954). The distinction between grain size and mineral composition in sedimentary rock nomenclature. *Jour. Geol.*, Vol. 62, pp. 344-359.
- International Lake Environment Committee (ILEC) (2005). "Chilka Lagoon – Experience and Lessons Learned brief. Asish, K. Ghosh, C. E. D. and Ajit, K. Patnaik, CDA. pp. 116-129.
- Iswaki, Shimpei. (1998). Sustainable Regional Development in the Catchment of Chilka Lagoon Orissa State. Proceedings of the International Workshop in Sustainable Development of Chilka Lake Tokyo Japan, Global Environment Information Centre, pp. 27.
- Krumbein, W. C. and Pettijohn, F. J. (1938). "Manual of Sedimentary Petrography." New York. D. Appleton-Century Co., Inc., 549 p.
- Krumbein, W. C. and Sloss, L. L. (1951). "Stratigraphy and Sedimentation." San Francisco, W.H. Freeman and Co., 497p.
- Muller, G. (1967). "Methods in Sedimentary Petrography" (English edition), Hafner Publishing Co., New York.
- Murray, A. S. and Mohanti, M. (2008). "Luminescence Dating of the Barrier Spit at Chilka Lake, Orissa, India". *Oxford Jour. Radiation Protection Dosimetry*. Vol. 119, No. 1-4, pp. 442-445.
- Patnaik, S. (1971). "Seasonal Abundance and Distribution of Bottom Fauna of the Chilka Lake." *Jour. Mar. Boil. Asso. India*, 13(1): pp. 106-125.
- Patnaik, S. (1987). "Distribution of in the Surficial Sediments of Chilka Lake", M.Phil, Thesis, Berhampur Univ., Berhampur, Orissa.
- Saxby, J.D., (2003). "Oil Generating Potential of Organic Matter in Sediments under Natural Conditions.". Division of Mineralogy C.S.I.R.O., Sydney, N.S.W. Australia
- Shepard, F. P. (1954). "Nomenclature based on Sand-Silt-Clay Ratios". *Jour. Sed. Petrol.*, Vol. 24, pp. 151-158.
- Singh, Sarina: Joe Bind Loss, Paul Clammer, Janine Eberle. (2005). *India, Lonely Planet*, pp. 576.
- Sun, Z., yang, F., and Zang, Z., (1997) "Condition of Sedimentation and Emergence of Petroleum in Cenozoic Saline Lake in China". Petroleum Industry Press. Beijing (in Chinese).
- Sverdrup, H. U., Johnson, M. W. and Fleming, R. H. (1942). "The Oceans Prentice-Hall, New York", 1087 p.
- Trask, P. D. (1939). "Organic Content of Recent Marine Sediments". In: A Symposium on Recent Marine Sediments, P.D. Trask (Editor), Tulsa, Amer. Assoc. Petrol. Geol., pp. 428-453.
- Trefethen, J. M. (1950). "Classification of Sediments". *Amer. Jour. Sci.*, Vol. 248, pp. 55-62.
- Tripathy, Balaran (2007-11). "Maritime Heritage of Orissa". Orissa Review (Govt. of Orissa): 27-41, pp. 27-41.
- Walkley, A.(1935). An examination of methods for determining organic carbon and nitrogen in soils. *Jour. Agri. Sci.*, Vol.25, P.598